

A DESCRIPTIVE STUDY ON THE EXPORT PERFORMANCE OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCT

M. Prasanth* & Dr. D. Santhanakrishnan**

Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: M. Prasanth & Dr. D. Santhanakrishnan, "A Descriptive Study on the Export Performance of Agricultural Product", International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education, Volume 4, Issue 1, Page

Number 84-86, 2018.

Copy Right: © IJMRME, R&D Modern Research Publication, 2018 (All Rights Reserved). This is an Open Access Article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract:

It is the agricultural sector that feeds country's trade. Agricultural products like tea, sugar, rice, tobacco, spices etc. constitute the main items of exports of India. If the development process of agriculture is smooth, export increases and imports are reduced considerably. The study clearly shows that export of fresh vegetables and fresh fruits are seeing an upfront growth. Still the exports can be increased if the governments supports by providing more incentives to the exporters. The study has thrown a light on agriculture industry and has induced the researcher to take up business associated with agri exports. We could also note that Government is supporting the agri industry and the role of APEDA in promoting exports is very vast.

Key Words: Agricultural Products, Government & Incentives

Introduction:

India is known as Land of Village Near about 67% of India population live in Village. The occupation of Villagers is agriculture. Agriculture is the dominant sector of our Economy. Despite the focus on industrialization, agriculture remains a dominant sector of the Indian economy both in terms of contribution to gross domestic product (GDP) as well as a source of employment to millions across the country. Agriculture plays a vital role in the Indian economy.

Agriculture for decades had been associated with the production of basic food crops. Agriculture and farming were synonymous so long as farming was not commercialized. But as the process of economic development accelerated, many more other occupations allied to farming came to be recognized as a part of agriculture.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ A study on APEDA.
- ✓ To study about the present scenario of export performance of agricultural products.
- ✓ To study about the agricultural products preserved by combined methods & packaging methods.
- ✓ To Study about the export procedure of Agricultural product and the Documents involved.
- ✓ To study about the incentives offered by Government.
- ✓ To Study about the Export performance of Agricultural product from India.
- ✓ To study about the Import performance of Agricultural product from India.

Scope of the Study:

- Importance of exporting agricultural product,
- ✓ Agricultural Exports Play an Important Role in a Country's Economy. Agriculture contributed National income of India
- ✓ Agricultural is giving employment opportunities to the people
- ✓ The Agricultural is Contributing the State revenue by Agricultural taxation includes Direct Tax and Indirect Tax.
- ✓ Agriculture plays important role in foreign trade attracting valuable foreign exchange, necessary for our economic development.

Needs for the Study:

- ✓ To identify the Agricultural exporting procedures.
- ✓ To know the documents involved in exporting on Agricultural products.
- ✓ To know the incentives offered by Government.
- ✓ To know the packaging method of agriculture products.
- ✓ To know the handling procedure of agriculture products.

Limitations of the Study:

Although utmost care will be taken in making this report a complete information regarding the subject, however changing scenario, changing government policies as well as the limited data available with the sources, moreover the methods used in gathering the data are the factors on which the report depends. These factors affect the report and so limit its scope on matter of the 100% coverage. It is also important to add that in such

case the reports of the magazines and above it the latest government policies should be approached. Mostly the data have been collected on the secondary basis (secondary data).

Methodology of the Study:

The basic knowledge about the workings of Agriculture product has to be gathered through the secondary data available on the internet and the documents available in the institute library. The quantum of information on this subject matter is enormous and updated. The secondary sources such as internet and news articles cover almost all major players. Research is a common parlance refers to search for knowledge. Research methodology is a way to systematically solve the research problem. Research is thus an original contribution to existing stock of knowledge for its advancement. In short, the research for knowledge through objective and systematic method of finding solution to the problem is research. Research methodology is a way to systematically solve the research problem. When we talk of research methodology we not only talk about research method but also consider the logic behind the research method we have used in the context of the research.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Export Performance of India:

India is exporting many products to other countries. But agricultural products are occupying number one position. The below table shows, list of top ten countries importing Fresh vegetables from India. The table is based on by quantity.

Table 4.1: Product - Other Fresh Vegetables

	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17
Country	Qty (Tonnes)	Qty (Tonnes)	Qty (Tonnes)
Pakistan	2,19,811.71	2,84,094.22	3,88,474.97
Nepal	1,70,760.82	1,84,036.47	1,87,963.71
United Arab Emirates	1,01,659.74	1,08,547.91	1,01,938.36
Sri Lanka	44,920.98	14,582.63	34,071.61
Bangladesh	30,124.34	11,919.08	44,787.47
Saudi Arabia	23,704.68	25,827.41	31,533.56
United Kingdom	22,521.60	20,792.11	20,907.56
Qatar	12,191.63	12,773.17	15,269.56
Kuwait	9,116.85	8,984.09	17,693.16
United States	8,545.51	6,734.99	6,435.28

Interpretation:

The table shows that India has exported fresh vegetables to many countries and the top three countries of export are Pakistan, Nepal, UAE for the period of 2014-2017.

Fresh Fruits:

	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17
Country	Qty (Tonnes)	Qty (Tonnes)	Qty (Tonnes)
United Arab Emirates	72,892.43	74,207.06	66,804.54
Bangladesh	82,477.11	73,839.12	83,273.96
Nepal	34,472.98	33,180.13	28,477.43
Saudi Arabia	19,095.70	20,789.09	18,848.87
Kuwait	6,065.38	5,030.17	5,270.78
Maldives	4,304.48	3,576.49	2,340.43
Oman	3,592.38	5,646.52	5,223.05
United Kingdom	2,983.25	2,556.73	1,416.46
Netherland	2,857.79	3,890.72	2,495.57
United States	1,521.41	1,683.05	1,114.66

Interpretation:

The table shows India has exported fresh fruits to many countries and the top three countries of export of fresh fruits are United Arab Emirates, Bangladesh, Nepal for the period of 2014-2017.

Import of Fresh Fruits by India:

	2016-17	2015-16	2014-15
Country	Qty (Tonnes)	Qty (Tonnes)	Qty (Tonnes)
Iraq	1,38,391.44	1,43,137.31	1,28,061.00
Pakistan	1,32,572.18	1,17,722.44	1,07,067.25
China P Rp	98,236.15	91,889.03	95,630.75
United States	52,939.77	77,870.32	80,022.92
Bangladesh	37,031.02	87,403.06	55,124.72
Iran	25,083.17	34,366.36	18,874.21

New Zealand	17,019.89	19,956.34	11,864.27
Chile	16,749.12	23,064.64	22,053.08
Afghanistan	11,341.09	11,660.34	11,590.40
Indonesia	2,455.56	3,080.36	7,515.63

Interpretation:

The table shows India has Imported fresh fruits from many countries and the top three countries of import of fresh fruits are Iraq, Pakistan, China for the period of 2014-2017.

Import of Fresh Vegetables by India:

	2016-17	2015-16	2014-15
Country	Qty (Tonnes)	Qty (Tonnes)	Qty (Tonnes)
Nepal	6,729.50	5,058.56	4,277.00
Thailand	278.56	390.7	276.4
United States	134.81	106.32	60.9
China P Rp	39	52.83	254.91
Spain	24	226.29	88.62
France	2.16	36.94	18.54
United Arab Emirates	0.3	2.92	26.15
Germany	0	0	28.85
Pakistan	0	0	178
Australia	0	0.07	72

Interpretation:

The table 4.4 shows India has imported fresh vegetables from many countries and the top three countries of import of fresh vegetables are Nepal, Thailand, United States for the period of 2014-2017.

Findings:

- ✓ The present status of India Agricultural industry is seeing an upfront growth.
- ✓ The Export procedure for agricultural products is quiet easy but the risk involved in terms of preservation and Time for exporting.
- ✓ The Documents required for export of agricultural product is not cumbersome.
- ✓ Out of the incentives offered by government Vishesh Krishi Upaj Yojana Scheme sounds good.
- ✓ India has exported vegetables and fruits for past three years in large quantities to Pakistan, UAE, and Nepal.
- ✓ Export of vegetables and fruits has seen growth in the year 2013-2014 compared to the previous years.
- ✓ Import of vegetables and fruits has seen reduction in the year 2013-2014 compared to the previous years.

Suggestions:

- ✓ Exporters have to still find some more preservatives so that the Agricultural products can be preserve for a longer time.
- ✓ Government can also introduce some more schemes for the welfare of the exporters.
- ✓ Exporters can also expand their export destination to nearby countries like Fareast.
- ✓ Though import of vegetables and fruits has seen a reduction in the year 2014-2017, still it has to reduced so that domestic suppliers are getting affected, specially the fruits.

Conclusion:

The study clearly shows that export of fresh vegetables and fresh fruits are seeing an upfront growth. Still the exports can be increased if the governments supports by providing more incentives to the exporters. The study has thrown a light on agriculture industry and has induced the researcher to take up business associated with agri exports. We could also note that Government is supporting the agri industry and the role of APEDA in promoting exports is very vast.

References:

1. Aaby, N. E., & Slater, S. F. (1989). Management influences on export performance: a review of the empirical literature 1978-1988. *International marketing review*, 6(4).
2. Koh, A. C. (1991). Relationships among organisational characteristics, marketing strategy and export performance. *International marketing review*, 8(3).
3. Aaby, N. E., & Slater, S. F. (1989). Management influences on export performance: a review of the empirical literature 1978-1988. *International marketing review*, 6(4).
4. Koh, A. C. (1991). Relationships among organisational characteristics, marketing strategy and export performance. *International marketing review*, 8(3).
5. Morgan, N. A., Kaleka, A., & Katsikeas, C. S. (2004). Antecedents of export venture performance: A theoretical model and empirical assessment. *Journal of marketing*, 68(1), 90-108.